

EMERGENT VEGETATION IN THE MAIN CANALS OF THE HS DTD IN THE REGION OF BAČKA

DEJANA DŽIGURSKI, ALEKSA KNEŽEVIĆ, LJILJANA NIKOLIĆ,
BRANKA LJEVNAIĆ-MAŠIĆ¹

SUMMARY: During many years of phytocoenological research of MCN Hs DTD channels in Bačka were found stands of emerged vegetation of alliance Phragmition communis W. Koch 1926 emend. Soó 1947. The aim of this study is an analysis of association stands: Scirpo-Phragmitetum W. Koch 1926, Typhetum angustifoliae Pign. 1953, Typhetum latifoliae G. Lang 1973, Sparganietum erecti Roll 1938 and Glycerietum maximae Hueck 1931 which were found in this anthropogenic ecosystem.

Key words: MCN Hs DTD, emerged vegetation, alliance Phragmition communis.

INTRODUCTION

The hydro system Danube-Tisza-Danube (Hs DTD) is a multi-purpose hydro system that regulates the waters in the regions of Bačka and Banat. Its canal network connects 80 urban locations in the two regions, helps their protection against surface waters, allows ground water management and supplies irrigation water for agricultural production, potable water for urban and industrial facilities and fresh water for fishponds. The canal network is also used for commodity transport by water, it takes and removes industrial wastewater and it also serves for recreation, sport and tourism. The total length of the main canals of Hs DTD is 930 km, of which 600 km are navigable. In terms of water table, Hs DTD is divided into 14 sections, eight of which are in the region of Bačka and six in Banat.

In the region of Bačka, the main canal network (MCN) of Hs DTD consists of the following canals: Bezdan-Baja, Vrbas-Bezdan, Kosančić-Mali Stapar, Prigrevica-Bezdan, Odžaci-Sombor, Bečej-Bogojevo, Bački Petrovac-Karavukovo, Novi Sad-Savino Selo and Jegrička canal. Their total length is 421 km.

Original scientific paper / *Originalni naučni rad*

¹Dejana Džigurski, Ph.D., Assis. Prof., Aleksa Knežević, Ph.D., Full Prof., Ljiljana Nikolić, Ph.D., Assoc. Prof., Branka Ljevnaić-Mašić, Ph.D., assis, Faculty of Agriculture, Trg D. Obradovića 8, Novi Sad, Serbia.

Corresponding author: Dejana Džigurski, Trg D. Obradovića 8, Novi Sad, Serbia, Tel. +381214853451, e-mail: dejana@polj.uns.ac.rs

The objective of this study was to analyze stands of the associations *Scirpo-Phragmitetum*, *Typhetum angustifoliae*, *Typhetum latifoliae*, *Sparganietum erecti* and *Glycerietum maximae* registered in the MCN of Hs DTD in the region of Bačka.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The phytocoenological study conducted in the course of the 2003-2006 growing seasons in the MCN of Hs DTD in the region of Bačka was carried out according to the standards of the Swiss-French school (Braun-Blanquet, 1964). The sampling surface size was 10-25 m². The syntaxonomic status of the identified communities was analyzed after Soó (1964-1980). Plant species were determined by standard determination keys (Josifović, ed., 1970-1977; Saric, ed., 1986; Tutin et al., 1964-1980; Felföldy, 1990).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stands of the following associations were found in the course of the several-year phytocoenological study of the MCN of Hs DTD in the region of Bačka: *Scirpo-Phragmitetum*, *Typhetum angustifoliae*, *Typhetum latifoliae*, *Sparganietum erecti* and *Glycerietum maximae* (Lazić, 2006). These associations belong to the emergent vegetation of the alliance *Phragmition communis* W. Koch 1926 emend. Soó 1947, the order *Phragmitetalia* W. Koch 1926 and the class *Phragmitetea* Tx. et Prsg. 1942.

Table 1. Plant communities of the alliance *Phragmition communis* in MCN DTD in Bačka
Tabela 1. Biljne zajednice iz sveze *Phragmition communis* u OKM Hs DTD u Bačkoj

	1a	1b	2	3	4	5
Characteristic species of the association / <i>Karakteristične vrste asocijacije</i>						
<i>Phragmites communis</i> Trin.	V ₃₋₅	IV ₁₋₃	III ₊₂	I ₊	II ₊₁	II ₊₂
<i>Schoenoplectus lacuster</i> (L.) Palla	I ₊	V ₃₋₅	I ₊	I ₂	I ₊	
<i>Typha angustifolia</i> L.	III ₊	I ₁	V ₃₋₅	II ₊₁	II ₊₁	I ₊
<i>Typha latifolia</i> L.		V ₊₁	II ₊₁	V ₃₋₅	I ₊	
<i>Sparganium ramosum</i> Huds.	II ₊				V ₃₋₄	
<i>Glyceria maxima</i> (Hartm.) Holm.	III ₊	III ₊₂	III ₊₃	III ₊₃	I ₊	V ₃₋₅
Characteristic species of the alliances / <i>Karakteristične vrste sveze</i>						
<i>Sagittaria sagittifolia</i> L.	I ₊		I ₊	I ₊		
<i>Acorus calamus</i> L.			I ₊			
Characteristic species of the class / <i>Karakteristične vrste klase</i>						
<i>Rumex hydrolapathum</i> Huds.	IV ₊	I ₁	IV ₊₁	II ₊₁	III ₊	IV ₊₂
<i>Lycopus europeus</i> L.	IV ₊		III ₊₁	I ₊	II ₊₁	
<i>Iris pseudacorus</i> L.	III ₊₁	I ₂		I ₁	II ₊₁	II ₊₁
<i>Butomus umbellatus</i> L.	III ₊₂		II ₊	I ₊₂	III ₊₁	IV ₊₁
<i>Sium latifolium</i> L.	II ₁₋₂		III ₊₁	II ₊₁	I ₁	
<i>Glyceria fluitans</i> (L.) R. Br.	I ₁	I ₁				
<i>Typhoides arundinacea</i> L.	I ₊					
<i>Roripa amphibia</i> (L.) Bess.		I ₊				
<i>Oenanthe aquatica</i> (L.) Poiret	I ₊		I ₊			II ₊

<i>Stachys palustris</i> L.	I ₊			II ₊	II ₊
<i>Alisma plantago-aquatica</i> L.	I ₊		I ₊	I ₊	
Accessory species / Vrste pratilice					
<i>Calystegia sepium</i> (L.) Br.	III ₊₁	I ₊	III ₊	II ₊	II ₊
<i>Bolboschoenus maritimus</i> (L.) Palla		IV ₊₁	I ₊		II ₊₂
<i>Carex pseudocyperus</i> L.	III ₊		II ₊	I ₊	II ₊₁
<i>Galium palustre</i> L.	III ₊	I ₊	II ₊₂	II ₊₁	II ₊
<i>Solanum dulcamara</i> L.	III ₊		II ₊	I ₊	II ₊
<i>Juncus articulatus</i> L.	I ₂				I ₊
<i>Heleocharis palustris</i> (L.) R. Br.		I ₂	I ₊		
<i>Epilobium hirsutum</i> L.	I ₁		I ₁		
<i>Catabrosa aquatica</i> (L.) P. B.	I ₁		I ₊	I ₂	II ₊
<i>Juncus compressus</i> Jacq.		I ₁	I ₊		
<i>Eupatorium cannabinum</i> L.	II ₊		I ₊	II ₊	
<i>Lythrum salicaria</i> L.	II ₊				
<i>Polygonum lapathifolium</i> L.	II ₊		I ₊	I ₊	I ₁
<i>Scutellaria galericulata</i> L.	II ₊		I ₊		I ₊
<i>Bidens tripartita</i> L.	I ₊		III ₊₁	I ₊	I ₊
<i>Angelica sylvestris</i> (Bess.) Hoffm.	I ₊				
<i>Typha laxmanni</i> Lepechin	I ₊				
<i>Polygonum hydropiper</i> L.	I ₊				
<i>Carex vulpina</i> L.		I ₊	I ₊	I ₊₁	II ₊₁
<i>Mentha aquatica</i> L.	I ₊		II ₊₁	I ₊	II ₊₁
<i>Solidago serotina</i> Ait.	I ₊				
<i>Epilobium adnatum</i> Gris.	I ₊				I ₊
<i>Urtica dioica</i> L.	I ₊				
<i>Lysimachia vulgaris</i> L.	I ₊				
<i>Poa palustris</i> L.	I ₊			I ₊	
<i>Ranunculus sceleratus</i> L.	I ₊			I ₊	I ₊
<i>Polygonum amphibium</i> L.		I ₊			II ₊₂
<i>Inula britannica</i> L.			I ₊		
<i>Cyperus fuscus</i> L.			I ₊		
<i>Juncus effusus</i> L.			I ₊		
<i>Verbena officinalis</i> L.			I ₊		
<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i> L.			I ₊		II ₊
<i>Potamogeton fluitans</i> Roth.					II ₊₃
<i>Trapa natans</i> L.					II ₁₋₂
<i>Ceratophyllum demersum</i> L.					II ₊₁
<i>Hydrocharis morsus-ranae</i> L.					II ₊₁
<i>Salvinia natans</i> (L.) Allioni					II ₊
<i>Lemna trisulca</i> L.					I ₂
<i>Vallisneria spiralis</i> L.					I ₊
<i>Potamogeton perfoliatus</i> L.					I ₊
<i>Najas marina</i> L.					I ₊

<i>Nuphar lutea</i> (L.) Sm.	I ₊
<i>Myriophyllum spicatum</i> L.	I ₊
<i>Xanthium italicum</i> L. Moretti	I ₁
<i>Torilis arvensis</i> (Huds.) Link.	I ₊
<i>Rumex conglomeratus</i> Murr.	I ₊
<i>Juncus gerardi</i> Lois.	I ₊

Legend: 1a - *Scirpo-Phragmitetum* subass. *phragmitetosum*; 1b - *Scirpo-Phragmitetum* subass. *schoenoplectetosum lacustris*; 2 - *Typhetum angustifoliae*; 3 - *Typhetum latifoliae*; 4 - *Sparganietum erecti*; 5 - *Glycerietum maximae*

1) Ass. *Scirpo-Phragmitetum* W. Koch 1926 (Tab. 1, col. 1)

The ass. *Scirpo-Phragmitetum* growing in the MCN of Hs DTD in the region of Bačka was found to form two subassociations: subass. *phragmitetosum* Schmale 1939 (Tab. 1, col. 1a) and subass. *schoenoplectetosum lacustris* Soó 1957 (Tab. 1, col. 1b).

Stands of *Scirpo-Phragmitetum* subass. *phragmitetosum* dominated the shallow waters along the banks of all investigated canals in Bačka. In the section from Zmajevó to Źabalj (Jegrička canal) and near the village of Mali Stapar (Kosančić-Mali Stapar canal), these stands spread to the middle of the canals. The flora of the stand was composed of 38 taxa. In addition to the dominant species *Phragmites communis*, the following species were found in large numbers and percentage cover: *Butomus umbellatus*, *Glyceria maxima*, *Typha angustifolia*, *Rumex hydrolapathum*, *Lycopus europaeus*, *Calystegia sepium*, *Iris pseudacorus*, *Carex pseudocyperus*, *Sium latifolium*.

Stands of *Scirpo-Phragmitetum* subass. *schoenoplectetosum lacustris* were formed at sites with deeper water than it was the case with the previously discussed subassociation, because the codominant species *Schoenoplectus lacuster* requires high moisture throughout the vegetation period. These stands were found only in Jegrička canal (near the village of Sirig and in Źabalj fishpond) where they were interspersed with stands of subass. *phragmitetosum*. The stands were floristically poor (16 taxa), with *Phragmites communis* and *Schoenoplectus lacuster* occurring in increased numbers. *Glyceria maxima*, *Typha latifolia* and *Bolboschoenus maritimus* were other important members of this biocoenosis.

2) Ass. *Typhetum angustifoliae* Pign. 1953 (Tab. 1, col. 2)

Stands of this phytocoenosis, usually small in size, grew in shallow water, up to 0.5 m deep, near canal banks. They were typically interspersed with stands of ass. *Scirpo-Phragmitetum*, less frequently with stands of ass. *Typhetum latifoliae* and ass. *Glycerietum maximae*. Towards the middle of the canals, these stands neighbored stands of the floating associations *Hydrocharidetum morsus-ranae*, *Nymphaeetum albo-luteae*, and *Lemno-Spirodeletum* and stands of the submerged associations *Elodeetum canadensis* and *Ceratophyllo demersi-Vallisnerietum spiralis* (DŹigurski et al., 2009).

The floristic composition of the association included 33 taxa, with the percentage cover generally ranging between 90-100%. The dominant species *Typha angustifolia* was found in large numbers and high percentage cover in all analyzed stands. The characteristic species of the class *Phragmitetea*, *Rumex hydrolapathum*, *Glyceria maxima*, *Phragmites communis*, *Lycopus europaeus* and *Sium latifolium*, were present in increased numbers. The species *Typha angustifolia* and *Rumex hydrolapathum* formed the characteristic group of plants.

3) Ass. *Typhetum latifoliae* G. Lang 1973 (Tab. 1, col. 3)

Hygrophilous stands of ass. *Typhetum latifoliae* were registered in shallow waters (0.2 to 0.5 m deep) of the studied ecosystem as well as on canal banks. These stands had a limited distribution, forming islands or belts that neighbored stands of ass. *Scirpo-Phragmitetum*. In the parts where they bordered the vegetation-free water surface, these associations were in contact with floating stands of ass. *Hydrocharidetum morsus-ranae*, ass. *Nymphaetum albo-luteae*, ass. *Trapetum natantis*, ass. *Salvinia-Spirodeletum polyrrhizae* and ass. *Lemno-Spirodeletum* as well as with submerged stands of ass. *Elo-deetum canadensis*.

The presence of 24 taxa indicated that the analyzed association was floristically poor. The total percentage cover was 90-100%. The dominant species *Typha latifolia* gave the physiognomic mark to these stands. *Sagittaria sagittifolia*, the characteristic species of the alliance, was registered in only one location and even there its numbers and percentage cover were low. Among the characteristic species of the class, the following species were distinguished for the presence, numbers and percentage cover: *Glyceria maxima*, *Rumex hydrolapathum*, *Sium latifolium* and *Typha angustifolia*. The characteristic group included only *Typha latifolia*, the dominant species of the community. The analyzed stands were heterogeneous with regard to their floristic structure.

4) Ass. *Sparganietum erecti* Roll 1938 (Tab. 1, col. 4)

Stand of the community *Sparganietum erecti* grew in the form of islands in water up to 1 m deep. A characteristic feature of the sites occupied by this phytocoenosis was significant fluctuations of water level (Stančić, 2007). In the ecological sequence towards the deeper water, the stands of this association bordered with floating stands of ass. *Hydrocharidetum morsus-ranae* and ass. *Nymphaetum albo-luteae*. Towards the bank, this association bordered with emerged stands of ass. *Scirpo-Phragmitetum* and ass. *Typhetum angustifoliae*. In the northern part of Jegrička canal, stands of ass. *Sparganietum erecti* covered in some places the entire width of the canal (Lazić et al., 2005).

The floristic composition of the community included 25 plant species, whose total percentage cover was 80-100%. The coverage of the community was due to large numbers and extensive spread of the dominant species of the community, *Sparganium ramosum*. Among the characteristic species of the class, the following species were distinguished for their presence, numbers and percentage cover: *Butomus umbellatus*, *Rumex hydrolapathum*, *Typha angustifolia*, *Iris pseudacorus*, *Phragmites communis*, *Stachys palustris* and *Lycopus europaeus*. As the stands of this phytocoenosis grew in the zone that was continuously covered with water, the number of accompanying plants was small and all of them were hydrophytes.

5) Ass. *Glycerietum maximae* Hueck 1931 (Tab. 1, col. 5)

Stands of this phytocoenosis were tolerant to large changes in water level and they grew at sites rich in organic matter. The dominant species, *Glyceria maxima*, formed very dense stands in which few other plants were able to survive (*Rumex hydrolapathum*, *Stachys palustris*, *Iris pseudacorus*, etc.). Stands of this phytocoenosis formed small or large islands, which bordered with stands of ass. *Scirpo-Phragmitetum* and ass. *Typhetum latifoliae*. Towards the middle of the canals, these stands were in contact with floating stands of ass. *Nymphaetum albo-luteae* and ass. *Lemno-Spirodeletum* and submerged stands of ass. *Ceratophyllo demersi-Vallisnerietum spiralis* (Džigurski et al., 2009).

The floristic composition of the community *Glycerietum maximae* included 26 plant species. Most of these stands were floristically poor. Their percentage cover that ranged from 80 to 100% was due to the numbers and cover of *Glyceria maxima*. The characteristic

species of the class were: *Rumex hydrolapathum*, *Butomus umbellatus*, *Phragmites communis*, *Iris pseudacorus*, *Oenanthe aquatica*, *Stachys palustris* and *Typha angustifolia*.

CONCLUSION

In the MCN of Hs DTD in the region of Bačka, the stands of the emergent vegetation of the alliance *Phragmition communis* were found to consist of the associations *Scirpo-Phragmitetum*, *Typhetum angustifoliae*, *Typhetum latifoliae*, *Sparganietum erecti* and *Glycerietum maximae*. These associations form belts or islands in shallow waters along the banks of the canals. In the locations of Zmajevó and Źabalj (Jegrička canal) and Mali Stapar (Kosančić-Mali Stapar canal), stands of the above vegetation tended to spread to the middle of the canals.

REFERENCES

- BRAUN-BLANQUET J.: Pflanzensociologie. Wien-New York, 1964.
- DŹIGURSKI, D., STOJANOVIĆ, S., KNEŹEVIĆ, A., NIKOLIĆ, LJ., LJEVNAIĆ, B.: Vegetation of the classes *Hydrochari-Lemnetea* Oberd. 1967 and *Potametea* Tx. et Prsg. 1942 in the canal Bački Petrovac-Karavukovo. Contemporary Agriculture, 58(1-2)40-45, 2009.
- FELFÖLDY, L.: Visugyi hidrobiologia 18-Kotet-Hinar haterarazo Korniezetvieldelmi es Teruletfejlestesi Miniszterium. Budapest, 1-144, 1990.
- JOSIFOVIĆ, M. (ed.): Flora SR Srbije I-IX. SANU, Beograd, 1970-1977.
- LAZIĆ, D.: Vaskularna flora i vegetacija OKM Hs DTD na području Bačke-stanje i uticaj na korišćenje i održavanje. Doktorska disertacija, PMF, Univerzitet u Novom Sadu, 1-198, 2006.
- LAZIĆ, D., ŠKORIĆ, M., STOJANOVIĆ, S., KNEŹEVIĆ, A., NIKOLIĆ, LJ.: Sintaxonomic review of the Vegetation of the Jegrička watercourse. Contemporary Agriculture, 54(3-4)269-274, 2005.
- SARIĆ, M. (ed.): Flora SR Srbije X. SANU, Beograd, 1986.
- SOÓ, R.: A magyar flóra és vegetáció rendszertani-növénnyöldrajzi kézikönyve I-VI. Akadémiai kiadó, Budapest, 1964-1980.
- STANČIĆ, Z.: Marshland vegetation of the class *Phragmito-Magnocaricetea* in Croatia. Biologia, Section Botany, Bratislava, 62(3)297-314, 2007.
- TUTIN, T. G., HEYWOOD, V. H., BURGESS, N. A., VALENTINE, D. H., WALTERS, S. M., WEBB, D. A. eds.: Flora Europaea I-V. Cambridge University press, Cambridge, 1964-1980.

EMERZNA VEGETACIJA OKM HS DTD U BAČKOJ

DEJANA DŽIGURSKI, ALEKSA KNEŽEVIĆ, LJILJANA NIKOLIĆ,
BRANKA LJEVNAIĆ-MAŠIĆ

Izvod

Višegodišnjim fitocenološkim istraživanjima kanala OKM Hs DTD na području Bačke konstatovane su sastojine emerzne vegetacije sveze *Phragmition communis* W. Koch 1926 emend. Soó 1947. Cilj rada je analiza sastojina asocijacija: *Scirpo-Phragmitetum* W. Koch 1926, *Typhetum angustifoliae* Pign. 1953, *Typhetum latifoliae* G. Lang 1973, *Sparganietum erecti* Roll 1938 i *Glycerietum maximae* Hueck 1931 konstatovanih u ovom ekosistemu.

Ključne reči: OKM Hs DTD, emerzna vegetacija, *Phragmition communis*.

Received / *Primljen*: 09.02.2011.

Accepted / *Prihvaćen*: 24.03.2011.